

LIMITED APPLICABILITY OF KOSTANECKI'S REACTION. THE INFLUENCE OF HALOGEN ATOM ON THE REACTION.

BY DUHKHAHARAN CHAKRAVARTI AND BROJESWAR MAJUMDAR.

The ketones, -e.g., 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone, 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone, 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone, 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone, 5-chloro-2-hydroxypropiofenone and 5-bromo-2-hydroxypropiofenone have been submitted to Kostanecki's reaction with (a) acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, (b) propionic anhydride and sodium propionate and (c) butyric anhydride and sodium butyrate and it has been found that the *o*-hydroxyacetophenones yield with sodium propionate and propionic anhydride coumarins and in other cases chromones are obtained.

The formation of an α -pyrone derivative in Kostanecki's reaction is not unusual as the intermediate acyl derivative may lose water yielding either an α -pyrone or a γ -pyrone (Wittig, Baugart and Richter, *Annalen*, 1925, 446, 155; Bargellini, *Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1925, 2, 261; Baker and Eastwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2906; Chadha, Mahal and Venkataraman, *ibid.*, 1933, 1460; Heilbron *et. al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1263; 1934, 1311, 1581; 1936, 295; *cf.* Chakravarti and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 689; Flynn and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 215).

In studying Simonis' reaction Chakravarti and co-workers found that the halogen atoms favoured the formation of chromones in monohydric

phenols and the present investigation was undertaken with a view to study Kostanecki's reaction on the halogenated aceto-, propio-, and butyrophenones and to find out whether the halogen atoms have any marked influence on the formation of γ -pyrones as in Simonis' reaction. The ketones, e.g., 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone, 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone, 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone, 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone, 5-chloro-2-hydroxypropiofenone and 5-bromo-2-hydroxypropiofenone have been submitted to Kostanecki's reaction with (a) acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, (b) propionic anhydride and sodium propionate, and (c) butyric anhydride and sodium butyrate.

The ketones have been prepared from the acetyl and propionyl derivatives of the halogenated phenols by heating with aluminium chloride (Fries' rearrangement). In course of the preparation of the above ketones it has been observed that in some cases an appreciable amount of the phenol was formed due to the deacylation but the formation of phenol was effectively overcome by heating the mixture of acetyl or propionyl derivative and aluminium chloride for $\frac{1}{2}$ —1 hour at 120° and not for only 10 minutes as recommended by Rosenmund and Schnurr (*Annalen*, 1928, 460, 84). In attempting to prepare the *o*-hydroxybutyrophenones from the butyryl derivatives of the phenols, it has been found that variation of temperature and the increase of the duration of baking with aluminium chloride does not increase the yield of the butyrophenone, which is always obtained in very poor yield and is contaminated with the phenol. In the case of *o*-chlorophenol propionate and *o*-bromophenol propionate, the propionyl group migrates to the *para* position to the hydroxyl group since the acetyl derivative is formed on acetylation with acetic anhydride and not α - or γ -pyrone as is the case with the *o*-hydroxyketones.

On heating any of the above *o*-hydroxyacetophenones with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride 3-acetylchromones are obtained. In order to establish the γ -pyrone structure of the products attempts have been made to condense the resulting 2-methylchromones with benzaldehyde in presence of sodium ethoxide (cf. Heilbron, Barnes and Morton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2569; Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129) in view of the reactivity of the 2-methyl group in γ -pyrone, but the styryl derivative is not formed. The 3-acyl group probably produces hindrance in the reactivity of the 2-methyl group. That the products obtained are not coumarins but chromones is proved by Wittig's method (Wittig, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 88; Heilbron, Hey and Lythgoe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1581). The absence of

any non-acylated chromone in the product is shown by the fact that no oxonium salt is obtained by passing hydrochloric acid gas into an ethereal solution of the substance (*cf.* Wittig, *Annalen*, 1925, **446**, 155).

The *o*-hydroxyacetophenones yield with sodium propionate and propionic anhydride coumarins, which are identical with the coumarins described by Chakravarti and Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 619) from the appropriate phenols and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate by Pechmann's reaction.

The *o*-hydroxypropiophenones, when heated with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, give exclusively chromones and not coumarins and the resulting 2-methylchromones are readily characterised by the formation of 2-styryl derivatives on condensation with benzaldehyde in the presence of sodium ethoxide. Similarly the products obtained by heating *o*-hydroxypropiophenones with sodium propionate and propionic anhydride are also chromones and no trace of coumarin could be detected by Wittig's method of separation of coumarins from chromones. It should, however, be noted that the 2-ethylchromones thus obtained, resist the formation of styryl derivatives with benzaldehyde or piperonal even under the experimental conditions recommended by Heilbron, Hey and Lowe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1311). Interesting results have been obtained while applying the standard method of separation of coumarins from chromones. 6-Chloro-2-ethyl-3 : 8-dimethylchromone, under Wittig's condition, regenerates the parent ketone, 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropiophenone, instead of the expected diketone. The isolation of the parent *o*-hydroxyketone establishes the γ -pyrone structure of the condensation product, as the alkaline hydrolytic fission of the chromones only and not of the coumarins can explain the formation of the original ketone.

In view of the non-reactivity of the 2-ethylchromones, described in this paper, towards benzaldehyde, 2-ethylchromones and the isomeric 4-ethylcoumarins, which are the possible products of the reaction, have been synthesised by unambiguous methods. Ethyl propionate has been condensed with the *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of molecular sodium (*cf.* Kostanecki *et. al.*, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 330, 471 ; 1901, **34**, 2942 *et. seq.* ; Wittig *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 88 ; *Annalen*, 1925, **446**, 155 ; Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1388) and the sodium salt of the diketone, thus obtained, is methylated directly and the final ring-closure, which involves the elimination of methyl alcohol, is effected by hydrobromic acid in glacial acetic acid solution. Thus the product, obtained from 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone and ethyl propionate, is identical in all respects with the

compound prepared from 5-chloro-2-hydroxypropiophenone and propionic anhydride and sodium propionate.

The *o*-hydroxypropiophenone does not undergo condensation with ethyl propionate and hence the condensation product of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with ethyl propionate has to be methylated.

The condensation products of the halogenated *o*-hydroxypropiophenones with sodium butyrate and butyric anhydride are also γ -pyrones and like the 2-ethylchromones the 2-propylchromones also do not give benzylidene derivative and regenerate the parent ketone by alkaline hydrolytic fission under Wittig's experimental condition.

The isomeric 4-ethylcoumarins, which are the alternative possible products of the above reaction, have also been synthesised (Chakravarti and Majumdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 136).

Thus a study of Kostanecki's reaction on the halogenated *o*-hydroxy-aceto- and propiophenones has revealed no marked influence of the halogen atom on the formation of γ -pyrones as in Simonis' reaction.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone.—The acetate of 4-chloro-2-methylphenol (20 g., b.p. 235°), prepared by the action of acetyl chloride on the phenol in the usual manner, was mixed with finely powdered aluminium chloride (20 g.) and the mixture heated at 120° for 20-30 minutes. The glassy mass was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and distilled in steam. The product obtained from the steam distillate was crystallised from dilute alcohol as light yellow needles, m.p. 70°, yield 15 g. (Found : Cl, 19.24. $C_9H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 19.38 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 283° (decomp.). (Found: N, 17·9. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 17·4 per cent).

5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone.—The propionate of 4-chloro-2-methylphenol (20 g., b.p. 249-252°), prepared by the action of propionyl chloride on the phenol, was heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at 120° with aluminium chloride (20 g.). The mixture was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and distilled in steam, and the solid obtained from the distillate was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 61°, yield 17 g. (Found: Cl, 17·90. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 17·88 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 205°. (Found: N, 16·30. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 16·44 per cent).

3-Chloro-4-hydroxypropiofenone was prepared from the propionate of *o*-chlorophenol (20 g., b. p. 230-34°) by heating with aluminium chloride (20 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was purified by distillation in steam and crystallised from benzene as colourless plates, m. p. 80°. (Found: Cl, 18·73. $C_9H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 19·24 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 155°/6 mm., which solidifies on keeping to colourless needles. (Found: Cl, 15·63. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 15·67 per cent).

3-Bromo-4-hydroxypropiofenone was prepared by heating the propionate of *o*-bromophenol (20 g., b. p. 245-60°) with aluminium chloride (20 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was finally purified by distillation in steam. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 130°. (Found: Br, 34·65. $C_9H_9O_2Br$ requires Br, 34·93 per cent).

5-Bromo-2-hydroxypropiofenone, obtained in the usual manner from the propionate of *p*-bromophenol (20 g., b.p. 250°) by heating with aluminium chloride (30 g.) for 30-40 minutes, was distilled in steam and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 78°, yield 16 g. (Found: Br, 34·72. $C_9H_9O_2Br$ requires Br, 34·93 per cent).

General Method for the Acetylation, Propionylation and Butyrylation of the Aceto- and Propiofenones.

A mixture of the *o*-hydroxyketone (4 g.), freshly fused sodium salt of the fatty acid (6-10 g.) and the anhydride of the acid (30-40 g.) was heated at 170-180° for about 12 hours. The reaction mixture was then

poured into water and heated on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to decompose the excess of acid anhydride and the solid was collected and crystallised from a suitable solvent. The products obtained by the acetylation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones and *o*-hydroxypropiophenones are described in Table I and the compounds prepared by the propionylation of *o*-hydroxyaceto- and propiophenones are described in Table II. Table III describes the compounds obtained by the butyrylation of *o*-hydroxypropiophenones.

Alkaline Hydrolysis of 6-Chloro-3 : 8-dimethyl-2-ethylchromone : Isolation of 5-Chloro-2-hydroxy-3-methylpropiophenone.—6-Chloro-2-ethyl-3 : 8-diethylchromone was dissolved in alcoholic sodium ethoxide solution and left overnight. The insoluble residue melted at 85° (mixed m.p. with the chromone). The solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether and the ether extract was repeatedly washed with cold alkali (5%) and then with water. On acidifying the alkaline wash with hydrochloric acid a solid was obtained which did not respond to the test of 1 : 3-diketone nor did it regenerate the original chromone on heating with glacial acetic acid and hydrochloric acid. It gives a deep violet colouration with ferric chloride and on crystallisation was found to be identical with 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-methylpropiophenone (m.p. and mixed m.p. 61°).

Synthesis of 6-Chloro-3-methyl-2-ethylchromone from 5-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone and Ethyl Propionate.—A mixture of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (9.5 g.) and ethyl propionate (22 g.) was added to molecular sodium (3.5 g.), the reaction flask being cooled in ice. The mixture was then heated for 1 hour on the water-bath, cooled and poured into powdered ice. The sodium salt separating was collected, washed with ether and dried. It was then suspended in dry acetone and methylated with the requisite quantity of methyl iodide. The excess of acetone was then distilled off and the residual oil was poured into water, extracted with ether, the ethereal extract was dried and ether removed, when a sticky mass was obtained. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator and then heated with acetic acid and hydrobromic acid (1 c.c.) for 1 hour on the water-bath. The mixture was then poured into water, when an oil separated which gradually solidified to a brown mass. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol and found to be identical with the product obtained by the interaction of 5-chloro-2-hydroxypropiophenone, propionic anhydride and sodium propionate (m.p. and mixed m.p. 123°).

TABLE I.
Acetylation of *o*-Hydroxyaceto- and propiophenones.

Name of the compound.	Molecular formula.	Ketone used.	M.p.	Analysis Found ;	Calc.	Remarks.
6-Chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-3-acetylchromone	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3Cl$	5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone	139°	Cl, 14.4% Cl, 14.177%	Colourless plates from alcohol.	
5-Chloro-2 : 6-dimethyl-3-acetylchromone	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3Cl$	5-Methyl-3-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone	131°	Cl, 13.75	Colourless plates from alcohol.	
6-Chloro-2 : 3 : 8-trimethylchromone	...	5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropiophenone	124°		Needles from alcohol (identical with the compound described by Chakravarti and Banerjee, <i>loc. cit.</i>)*	
—Styryl derivative **	...		166-167°			
5-Chloro-2 : 3 : 6-trimethylchromone **	...	5-Methyl-3-chloro-2-hydroxypropiophenone	154-156°			
—Styryl derivative**	...		183°			
6-Chloro-2 : 3-dimethylchromone	...	5-Chloro-2-hydroxypropiophenone	86.87°		Identical with the compound described by Wittig (<i>Annalen</i> , 1925, 446, 186.	
—Styryl derivative	...		144-145°			
6-Bromo-2 : 3-dimethylchromone	...	5-Bromo-2-hydroxypropiophenone	113°		Identical with the compound prepared by Simonis from <i>p</i> -bromophenol and ethyl α -methylacetate.	

* The m. p. of 6-chloro-2 : 3 : 8-trimethylchromone was recorded as 113° by Chakravarti and Banerjee, but the compound prepared again by the application of Simonis' reaction on 4-chloro-2-methylphenol and ethyl α -methylacetate was found to melt at 124°.

** *cf.* Chakravarti and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*

TABLE II.
Propionylation of o-Hydroxyaceto- and propiophenones.

Name of the compound	Molecular formula.	Ketone used.	M. p.	Found.	Analysis Calc.	Remarks.
6-Chloro-3:4:8-trimethyl- coumarin	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-3-methyl- 2-hydroxyaceto- phenone	94°	Cl, 15.64%	Cl, 15.95%	Pale yellow needles from alcohol (b.p. 180-200°/6mm).
8-Chloro-3:4:6-trimethyl- coumarin	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2Cl$	5-Methyl-3-chloro-2- hydroxyaceto- phenone	157*	15.64	15.95	Identical with the compound prepared by Chakravarti and Banerjee (<i>loc. cit.</i>) from 2-chloro-4-methylphenol and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate.
6-Chloro-3:8-dimethyl- 2-ethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-3-methyl-2- hydroxypropio- phenone	85°	15.3	15.0	Does not give styryl derivative. It regenerates 5-chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropiphenone on hydrolysis.
8-Chloro-3:6-dimethyl- 2-ethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$	5-Methyl-3-chloro-2- hydroxypropio- phenone	74-75°	15.2	15.0	Needles from alcohol. It gives 5-methyl-3-chloro-2-hydroxypropiphenone on hydrolysis.
6-Chloro-2-ethyl-3-methyl- chromone	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-2-hydroxy- propiophenone	65-66°	15.7	15.9	Needles from alcohol. It is identical with the chromone obtained from 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone and ethyl propionate (<i>vide supra</i>).
6-Bromo-2-ethyl-3-methyl- chromone	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2Br$	5-Bromo-2-hydroxy- propiophenone	87°	Br, 29.87	Br, 29.96	Colourless needles from alcohol.

TABLE III.

Butyrylation of o-Hydroxypropiofenones.

Name of the compound.	Molecular formula	Ketone used.	M. p.	Analysis.		Remarks.
				Found.	Calc.	
6-Chloro-3-β-dimethyl-2-propylchromone	$C_{14}H_{15}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-3-methyl-2-hydroxypropio-phenone	95°	Cl, 13.85%	Cl, 14.17%	Crystallised from alcohol.
8-Chloro-2-propyl-3-β-dimethylchromone	$C_{14}H_{15}O_2Cl$	5-Methyl-3-chloro-2-hydroxypropio-phenone	68.71°	14.18	14.17	Colourless needles from alcohol. It regenerates 5-methyl-3-chloro-2-hydroxypropio-phenone on hydrolysis.
6-Chloro-2-propyl-3-methylchromone	$C_{15}H_{17}O_2Cl$	5-Chloro-2-hydroxy-propiofenone	85°	15.09	15.00	Colourless plates from alcohol.
6-Bromo-2-propyl-3-methylchromone	$C_{15}H_{17}O_2Br$	5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-propiofenone	83.84°	Br, 28.0	Br, 28.48	Needles from alcohol